

The charter is the foundational document that describes the rationale, goals, plan of work, resources needed, terms and conditions, and outcomes of a Center for Digital Humanities at Princeton (hereafter CDH) project. Charters are written by core members of a project team in a series of planning meetings taking place over the course of a month. The planning process is intensive, collaborative and requires substantial input from everyone on a team. Charters serve as formalized agreements among all team members on such crucial questions as scope, technical design, infrastructural needs, and success criteria.

A draft of each project charter is peer-reviewed by all CDH staff, and optionally by additional partners or stakeholders, at a “design review” before the start of project work. It is circulated at least one week before the review takes place in an open comment period. Questions and concerns from this period may be raised at the design review. Project teams have two weeks after the design review to address any issues raised and make any requested changes. Project work only begins (and funds are released) once the charter has been finalized and signed by the Project Director (PI) and the CDH Faculty Director. Charters are amended as necessary throughout the project lifecycle to document major changes and note when “Built by CDH” Software Warranty and “Built by CDH” Long Term Service Agreement take effect, and serve as part of the CDH project archive.

CDH charters and their planning documents exist in several forms as we have refined them over the years and tailored them to the several types of projects we have supported. For more about CDH project management, including the charter process, visit: <https://cdh.princeton.edu/research/project-management/>

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CDH Project Charter - bitKlavier

2017-18

Part I: Project Summary

1. Project Description & Objectives

bitKlavier is a digital tool for exploring a range of musical and creative ideas, including tuning and temperament, rhythm and meter, human-machine interaction, instrument design, performance practices, pedagogy, and composition.

This past year we made the consequential decision to completely redevelop bitKlavier from scratch in C++ using the open-source C++ framework JUCE; as of early August, this enabled us to release a beta-version of the application for Mac in both standalone and plugin (VST and AU) formats, as well as making the source openly available on Github; both were major goals of the last year. This new version is significantly faster than the original and the new code-base is clean and well setup for further development; rather than simply being a reproduction of the original, this new version has been completely redesigned to take advantage of the flexibility possible with C++.

Our objectives for the coming year are detailed in part 5 below, but the broad overview is as follows:

- Thoroughly beta-test this version; this process has already begun and will continue this fall, including students from Trueman's freshman seminar (Musical Instruments, Sound, Perception, and Creativity). Follow this with a public release.
- Target more platforms (iOS and Windows, more plugin formats)
- Expand the sound palette through some form of sample library import mechanism
- Implement network synchronization capability
- Enhance the functionality in a number of ways, possibly including:
 - import/export of individual preparations
 - new adaptive tempo and tuning algorithms
 - OSC API for control of bitKlavier preparation parameters
 - scripting
- Embed unit-testing into the code-base and our development practices.

2. Statement of Significance and Innovation

Digital musical instrument building resides at the murky but charged border between body and computer. On the one hand, we are trying to imagine how we might physically and intuitively relate to sound in expressive, qualitative ways, and on the other hand we are required to code that relationship in precise terms. Our code inevitably fails, either because of deficiencies in our coding or issues with the ideas we are trying to code; put another way: while coding up our theories, we learn about issues with both the theory itself and the digitizing of that theory. Part of "testing" what we have built involves using our bodies, leveraging whatever training we have embedded there through years of practice—playing the instrument—and asking ourselves questions about the richness of our experiences with the new instrument; the feedback loop between qualitative and quantitative thinking closes and repeats, revealing advantages to having the coder and musician be one and same. In a

general sense, then, part of the significance of this project should manifest itself in the ways quantitative and qualitative approaches to understanding can be reconciled, and how we can learn from our failures (which in and of themselves might be fascinating if unexpected).

The implications of our approach to digital instrument building play out in how we make music with others, how we listen, and how our instrument and its music is ultimately received. Does our instrument trivialize the performer, or enable her to reach new places? Does our instrument simply duplicate what existing instruments already provide, or does it offer something new that is indigenous to the digital world? Finally, how are familiar music making contexts transformed when these new instruments are introduced or, more simply, how do we make music together with these instruments? Our answers to these questions should reach beyond music and teach us something about simply being together, digitally or otherwise.

3. Audience

Our audience includes musicians of all sorts, but specifically composers, theorists, piano teachers and students, music producers.

4. Project team

Dan Trueman (Professor of Music/PI)
Mike Mulshine '16 (Developer/Research Assistant)
Florent Ghys GS (Project Manager)
Rebecca Sutton Koeser (Technical Advisor)
Xinyi Li (User Experience Designer)
Rebecca Munson (Project Designer)
Sarah Meadows (Business and Finance Administrative Coordinator)

5. Main project outcomes (deliverables, products). Include also what is out of scope.

In scope:

- Public release of OSX version of bitKlavier (potentially via the App Store)
- New iPad version; the current iOS version was made with the old code-base.
- AAX plugin version; this will enable use with ProTools, which does not work with VST and AU plugins.
- a Windows version; JUCE's cross-platform framework *should* allow this, and we have successfully compiled an early Windows version, but we still need to determine how much of an investment this would require to make fully usable.
- Sample-library import capability, to expand the sound palette, probably using the non-proprietary sFz format (<http://ariaengine.com/overview/sfz-format/>)
- Individual preparation export and import capability
- Basic unit-testing
- CDH-hosted workshop

Possibly in scope:

- iPhone version
- Network synchronization capability, via Ableton Link
- A new adaptive tempo implementation (exponential moving average)
- A new adaptive tuning implementation (“spring” tuning)
- Various extensions to current preparations:
 - Extend and expose audio envelope control to the user, for both synchronic and nostalgic preparations
 - Multiple keymaps for synchronic, to enable independent phase synchronization of pulse and parameter cycles, and pitch
 - “Gliss”; pitch shifting during note-length in both synchronic and nostalgic
- Scripting, via javascript, for both piano configuration (setting up the instrument) and parameter iteration (to script changes while the instrument is being played)
- Social media sharing of galleries
- More bitKlavier workshops and outreach

Likely out of scope:

- New preparation types (“blendrónic” and spectral phase vocoder)
- Additional physical interface support (ROLI Seaboard Block, MalletKat, etc...)
- Android support
- Live sampling

7. Resource needs

- Funding for Mulshine’s position, for development hours (half of his full-time appointment)
- CDH staff time:
 - continued consultation regarding code-base and open-source
 - Unit-testing development support
 - UX consultations

8. Risks

Most of the risks are due to unknowns developing for new platforms and interfaces. JUCE provides support for iOS, Windows, Linux, and Android development, so we are in a good position to manage these risks, but it remains unclear how much development time it will take to, for instance, enable our code to work well with iOS touch interfaces, or be usable under Windows. The AAX plugin format is dependent on Avid’s SDK, and, as noted below, could cause problems supporting that particular format.

9. Interdependencies

Our primary dependency is on the JUCE framework, which is under constant development with many commits per day to the development branch and 2–3 main releases per year; we feel confident that

this dependency will not be a hindrance, and in fact will be a great resource for years to come. VST development is dependent on Steinberg's SDK, which has long been in use. The AAX development is more problematic, as Avid's business practices make it significantly more difficult to develop with their SDK; again, JUCE provides support for this and we think we should be able to manage this format as well. Ableton Link is dependent on their new SDK; it looks straightforward, but as with anything like this, we won't be sure until we actually try to use it.

10. Project change process

Any significant changes **related to CDH Roles and Responsibilities only (see Workplan)** must be discussed and approved by the PI and the CDH Associate Director. These changes will be recorded and appended to the Project Charter. The CDH Project Designer will assure that an amendment is completed within a two-week time-frame.

11. Rights and permissions:

Galleries we release with the app will be covered by a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

12. Data security considerations

N/A

13. Data management plan

N/A

14. Post-grant plans for project

We have already secured a commitment from the Music Department to extend Mulshine's position indefinitely.

15. Any other issues

Part II: Design Plan

Application overview. Complete documentation of the application is beyond the scope of this document, but a broad overview is provided here for context.

bitKlavier's main window consists of a "construction area" where elements are connected in various ways (the "graph") to "prepare" the digital piano:

Figure 1: bitKlavier main window

In this example, the piano is prepared with the three main preparations available in bitKlavier: Direct (D), Synchronic (S), and Nostalgic (N). All three are connected (via yellow “cords”) to a Keymap which determines which piano keys activate those preparations. Each is also connected to its own Tuning preparations (green, with tuning fork icon), implying that each uses a different tuning. The synchronic preparation is connected to its own Tempo object (brown, with metronome icon) that sets the fundamental tempo of the synchronic preparation.

These objects can be moved around the construction area, connected in various ways, new preparations can be added, and so on, to create a particular set of behaviors; we refer to a configuration like this simply as a *piano*. Objects can be opened (via double-click) to reveal preparation-specific parameters that can be modified:

Figure 2: inside the Synchronic preparation

At the top of Figure 1 we have five menus (though one, the central Load Samples menu, is soon to be moved); these enable organization and saving in various ways. To the right, we have the Pianos (showing the currently selected piano, “Etude1-Prelude” in the example above) and Piano Action menus; at any particular time, we may have several pianos loaded and available (to enable rapid, player-driven switching between pianos; the instrument can change during performance), and this menu both displays which piano is currently open and active as well as allowing the user to manually switch to another piano.

Pianos are gathered into *galleries*, and galleries are managed via the Galleries and Gallery Action menus to the left. All of the pianos and their settings can be saved to disc here as XML files, and the gallery menu directly reflects the directory structure of the user’s own “galleries” folder.

The Action menus allow for various manipulations of of the pianos and galleries. To the left of the main window is a level meter for monitoring audio levels, to the right is a basic volume slider for controlling volume, and at the bottom is a keyboard UI which can be used to play the instrument and also display input from an external hardware keyboard.

Codebase. bitKlavier is written in C++ using the [JUICE](#) audio development framework. JUICE is powerful and cross-platform, and also under constant and active development, with hourly commits to its dev branch from the lead developers. It is the ideal platform for this project in that it is efficient and handles many of the core tasks that are shared by all audio application, from I/O to UI features. It includes a IDE

called the Projucer that exports projects to Xcode and other mainstream IDEs, wrapping in the needed support code depending on the development target (OSX, iOS, Windows, Android, etc....). We work primarily in Xcode, but when new C++ files are created, or JUCE is updated, we return to the Projucer to re-export; this has been a largely seamless process. Anyone working with the bitKlavier source-code would need to become familiar with JUCE and the Projucer to work with it effectively.

We have adopted the [model-view-controller](#) architecture for bitKlavier, which organizes the code into a back-end, where the audio is manipulated (the model), a collection of front end UI elements (the view), and code which connects the two (the controller). This is clearly reflected in the organization of the code. Again, complete documentation of the codebase is beyond the scope of this document, but suffice it to say that within each of these folders we have bitKlavier specific code for all the preparation types. New features are either extensions of existing functionality, functionality that is already supported by JUCE (including plugin export capability, JavaScript) or there are known implementations with JUCE that can be adapted (i.e. sFz sample format support).

Minimum Viable Product

In early August '17 we released a beta-version of bitKlavier for OSX and we currently have 30+ users. This fall, students in Trueman's freshman seminar will use the application as well and become active testers. This release includes "standalone" and "plugin" versions; the standalone behaves like a normal self-contained application and the plugins (VST and AU formats) work within host applications like Logic and Sibelius.

Our MVP includes a public release of bitKlavier (possibly via the App Store for the standalone) for OSX, along with the following:

1. A new iPad version; the currently available iPad version was written in our old architecture and does not have a future, other than through migration to this new version.
2. An AAX plugin version; AAX is Avid's plugin format, and allows usage with ProTools, a widely used production tool.
3. Sample-import capability; currently, bitKlavier works only with a single library or piano samples, and the most commonly requested feature is the ability to use other sample libraries. This is not just a cosmetic enhancement; working with different sound types (organs, harpsichords, percussion, etc...) will raise interesting questions about the nature of the instrument and the broader ideas it engages.
4. Individual preparation import/export capability; we currently can only save galleries of pianos, and would like to be able to share individual components (preparations). This will enhance workflow and collaborative possibilities.
5. Implementation of basic unit-testing. At this point we have not created any unit-testing, and would like to have that integrated into our workflow.

Possibly (hopefully) in-scope

In addition, we hope to implement as many of the features listed in Part I-5 as we can manage. These fall into three broad categories:

1. *Platform support*; we aim to make bitKlavier as widely accessible as we can manage, and JUCE supports Windows, iOS, and Android development. We don't currently have plans for Android, but are already working on both Windows and iPhone versions.

2. *Existing feature enhancement*; some of these are significant enough to explicitly list (for instance, both adaptive tuning and adaptive tempo additions would be significant, as would enveloping for nostalgic and synchronic preparations), whereas others are subtle improvements on the current functionality (piano menu organization capability, for instance).
3. *New features*; networking via Ableton Link and scripting would both be significant new additions that we are eager to work on during the upcoming year.

Application flow diagram (created by Xinyi):

PDF Version:

<https://drive.google.com/open?id=OB4Px2f82Hpt2ToNlX2F2VmFrOFE>

Part III Work Plan

We plan to work towards our MVP in this order:

1. Windows and iPad platform development; we plan to begin by getting the current beta working properly under Windows (if possible) and for iPad. Ideally, we make these available Trueman’s seminar students this fall semester. Depending on how the iPad development goes, we would also aim to have the iPhone version available. We feel that the current beta establishes a baseline state of the tool and codebase that makes sense to push to these other platforms as much as we can before extending. Mulshine will take the lead on these, Trueman will act as first tester.

2. Preparation import/export; this is a relatively simple feature to implement. Trueman/Mulshine will do in tandem.
3. Sample-library import; this is more involved, but there is ample code already available open-source, so we imagine this should be doable this fall. This may force us to implement the “enveloping” capability that we’ve listed as “possibly in scope,” which shouldn’t be too difficult. Trueman/Mulshine will do in tandem.
4. Basic unit-testing integration; this is one area where we would love CDH support, to the extent possible.

Once these are done or underway, we plan to work in tandem on the “possibly in-scope” elements in this order:

1. Ableton Link; this looks to be a relatively straightforward addition, and one that would be great to experiment with the students in Trueman’s seminar, as well as with the Princeton Laptop Orchestra.
2. Enveloping in Synchronic and Nostalgic, unless we’ve already taken it in as part of the sample-library extension.
3. New adaptive tempo
4. New adaptive tuning
5. Scripting; this is likely a big addition, one that will take some time and thought, and one that we hope will lay the groundwork for future development, so it remains unclear exactly how will proceed. JUCE provides support for Javascript, and we plan to start there with scripted preparation definition (so parameters can be set via some kind of simple function rather than manually) and then go from there. This will benefit the backend coding work whether or not it is exposed to end users in the user interface.

Of course, each of these will likely present surprises of various sorts, so it’s inevitable that these plans will change to some extent, but this looks like a reasonable roadmap to start.

We should also note that all of this will be tempered by the inevitable bug-fixing that will arise; we are already identifying and fixing bugs, as well as refining various features of the current design, and some of these refinements actually take a fair bit of time.

Projected Schedule:

Phase 1: platform viability assessment (first half of September)

Mulshine explores issues involved with targeting Windows, iOS (both iPad and iPhone), AAX/RTAS. Develop platform priorities.

Phase 2: new platforms (mid-September to mid-November)

Probably iOS first, followed by Windows. AAX/RTAS should be simple, assuming permission from Avid. Also begin exploring unit-testing options.

Phase 3: debugging, preparing for launch (mid-November to mid-January)

If time permits, begin exploring Ableton Link and sample-library import.

January ‘18—Public Launch (all workable platforms)

Phase 4: preparation export/import, new sample libraries and networking, continued debugging (mid-January to mid-March)

February/March—CDH Hosted Public Workshop

Phase 5: scripting, adaptive tempo, adaptive tuning (mid-March to mid-June)

Phase 6: paper writing, online sharing mechanism (mid-June to August)

CDH Roles and Responsibilities:

1. Discuss scripting for MVP (RK and XL)
2. Visual design support (XL)
3. Support for developing scaling/touch for iPhone (XL)
4. Development and support for unit testing; propose initial framework for team to adapt and apply (RK)
5. Standing monthly meeting with CDH staff for questions/support (RM, RK, XL, others if needed)
6. A workshop during the month of February (RM, SM, other staff as needed)

Part IV Budget.

[Budget available upon request.]

Part V Agreement

This document represents mutual agreement on the deliverables, responsibilities and timeline necessary for project success. It binds both parties to the terms and expectations set out above.

Rights, Permissions, and Attribution

Galleries released with the app will be covered by a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Credit

All team members will be credited on the project's website and CDH publicity page. The project's website will include a sponsorship statement (indicating the CDH as well as any other supporting groups, departments, agencies) and will include statement indicating how the project assets should be cited.

Project PI

CDH Associate Director

Date
